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Simulations of CO₂ droplet release on Norwegian waters

To support the application to the Norwegian state pollution authorities.

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1 Simulations and set-up.

The simulations were performed to support the application by Norwegian Institute for Water Research, on behalf of the international experiment consortium, to perform a small scale experiment off the Norwegian coast.

The model used is a two-phase droplet plume model in which droplets interact with seawater through mass-transfer and drag. It is thoroughly described in Alendal et al. (1998) and Alendal and Drange (2001).

Environmental parameters were taken from in-situ measurements at Haltenbanken, situated close to the experimental site. A total of six numerical experiments was conducted, with different injection rate, initial droplet size, and background current, as shown in Tab. 1. The injection rate was constant through the integration of one hour.

Case	Injection rate Kg/s	Droplet radius m	Background current m/s
A	0.1	0.002	0.05
B	0.1	0.002	0.20
C	0.1	0.002	0.50
D	0.6	0.002	0.05
E	0.6	0.002	0.20
F	0.6	0.004	0.50

Table 1: Characteristic parameters for the six numerical experiments performed.

2 Results and discussion

After the initial transient phase, approximately 10 minutes, the droplet plume reaches a quasi steady state, Fig. 1. Droplets rise through the water column and, due to interfacial drag, entrain sea water. The entrained water experience increased CO_2 concentration due to the gradual dissolution of the droplets. This CO_2 enriched water is transported downstream by the background current and tend to sink due to increased density.

Fig. 2 show the droplet plume after 50 minutes integration for the different simulations. The differences between Cases A, B, and C are the background current. The plume stand with an angle to the vertical that increases with increasing current. Notice that the rising distance of the droplet plume is similar, this because the vertical slip velocity is not dependent on the horizontal current. When the injection rate increases, Cases D, E, and F, the droplet plume becomes more evident. If in addition the initial droplet size is doubled the rising distance also increase. Larger droplets have higher slip velocity and contain more mass.

The down stream transport of CO_2 enriched seawater is shown in Fig. 3. With higher background current the pH reduction is less. This is due to higher flux of seawater through the droplet plume, hence the CO_2 is dissolved into larger water masses. With increasing injection rate the pH-reduction is larger, more CO_2 enters the system. The low pH-reduction in Fig. 3(f) is due to the higher rising distance of the droplets, which further increase the volume of sea water affected by the injected CO_2 .

References

- G. Alendal, H. Drange, and F. Thorkildsen. Twophase modelling of CO_2 droplet plumes. Technical Report 153, Nansen Environmental and Remote Sensing Center, Bergen, Norway, 1998.
- G. Alendal and H. Drange. Two-phase, near-field modeling of purposely released CO_2 in the ocean. *J. Geophys. Res.*, 106(C1):1085–1096, 2001.

Figure 1: Case A; Time evolution of ICO₂, liquid CO₂ remaining inside droplets, and *pH*-value. The cross-section cut through the injection site in the along stream direction.

Figure 2: ICO₂ comparison between the six numerical experiments after 50 minutes.

Figure 3: pH -field comparison between the six numerical experiments after 50 minutes.